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Full Length Article

Effect of Zr addition on the corrosion resistance of Ti-Mo alloy in the H₂O₂-containing inflammatory environment

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ABSTRACT

Reactive oxygen species (ROS), produced by immune cells during inflammatory reaction, are known to promote corrosion of standard biomedical materials such as CP-Ti and Ti-6Al-4V. Electrochemical corrosion in the ROS environment can be further accelerated in the vicinity of fretting regions, where titanium can be polarized towards negative potentials. This study considers both of these aspects and presents corrosion analysis under complex inflammatory conditions for Ti-Mo and Ti-Mo-Zr alloys, which offer exceptional strain-hardening behavior and ductility. Combining electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and atomic emission spectroelectrochemistry (AESEC) allowed us to understand the origin of ROS-induced corrosion. At free corrosion conditions, Zr was found to suppress oxide layer growth without any significant effect on the dissolution process. On the other hand, Zr suppressed dissolution rate under cathodic potentials. Although applying cathodic potential resulted in a rapid increase of dissolution rate, cross-section transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis did not reveal significant influence of the short cathodic polarization on the oxide film growth during further prolonged exposure at free corrosion conditions.

1. Introduction

One of the key challenges in the modern biomedical field is ensuring that permanent implants can serve long-term without needing replacement during a patient's lifetime [1,2]. Titanium biomaterials are considered as a first choice for permanent orthopedic and dental implantable devices due to their superior mechanical properties and biocompatibility compared to other metal-based materials used in the biomedical industry [3–6]. Currently, Ti-12Mo alloys are receiving particular attention owing to their combination of high strain hardening rate and excellent level ductility, which is hard to achieve for other titanium alloys [7,8]. The exceptional strain-hardening behavior and the consequent ductility of the Ti-12Mo alloy are attributed to the simultaneous activation of additional deformation mechanisms alongside dislocation slip, precisely Twinning Induced Plasticity (TWIP) and/or Transformation Induced Plasticity (TRIP) [9]. Considering biomedical

applications, Ti-12Mo alloys also demonstrate satisfactory biological response, which has been confirmed by *in vitro* cytotoxicity examination [10] and *in vivo* biomechanical tests on the rat model [11]. From the application perspective, the success of implantation procedure also depends on the biomaterials corrosion properties. Advantageous corrosion properties compared to the commercially used Ti-based materials such as Ti-6Al-4V [10] and CP-Ti [11] have been already confirmed in the standard physiological solutions, such as phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). However, further corrosion evaluation of Ti-12Mo is required in the conditions, which more truly reflect the complexity of the peri-implant environment.

The implantation procedure triggers inflammatory reaction, which in turn involves generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [12–15]. ROS that are produced by immune cells such as neutrophils or macrophages [16], can be immediately transformed into hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) in the enzymatically catalyzed reaction by superoxide dismutase

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(SOD) [17]. H_2O_2 adversely affects the corrosion resistance of titanium by increasing its dissolution rate [18], and can induce the growth of an oxide with porous morphology [19,20]. The origin of this phenomenon can be attributed to formation of $Ti-H_2O_2$ complexes and to the accelerated oxidation of Ti in the H_2O_2 -rich solution [12,18,21,22]. Corrosion in the H_2O_2 -contained fluids can be further accelerated at cathodic potentials [21,23,24]. It is claimed that both H_2O_2 and cathodic polarization can promote generation of anion vacancies within titanium oxide layer. Moreover, more defects can be created in the oxide when the material is exposed to H_2O_2 and cathodic potentials simultaneously [25]. Titanium orthopedic implants can become polarized to negative potentials under fretting conditions. *In vitro* studies have shown that electrochemical potential of Ti-6Al-4V can drop to as low as $-1V$ during tribocorrosion [26]. Micro-movements between two parts of orthopedic replacement can damage the titanium oxide film, which enforces its spontaneous re-healing due to titanium's high affinity for oxygen [27–29]. Rebuilding of the oxide layer requires oxygen, which can lead to deaeration of the small volume of body fluids trapped in the crevices between the contacting surfaces [30,31]. Due to this oxygen depletion, electrons can accumulate on the implant's surface, causing the material to polarize towards negative values [24]. Cathodic polarization occurs not only within the fretting area but also in the adjacent regions [32]. This highlights importance to consider possible corrosion consequences of fretting process in the non-mechanically damaged parts of implants.

The clinical significance of H_2O_2 -induced corrosion enforces development of new ways to suppress this process, such as modifying chemical composition of biomaterials [12,15,33]. Electrochemical studies revealed that the addition of Zr to Ti can suppress its corrosion in the H_2O_2 -rich physiological fluid [34]. The reason of this phenomenon is still not clear but it is hypothesized that the beneficial role of Zr can be related to the following factors: (i) higher stability of ZrO_2 compared to TiO_2 owing to the higher energy of Zr-O bonds (766 kJ/mol) compared to Ti-O bonds (666 kJ/mol), (ii) the possibility of catalyzing H_2O_2 decomposition by ZrO_2 oxide, (iii) lack of tendency to complexation reaction between H_2O_2 and Zr or ZrO_2 [15,34]. Findings related to the behavior of binary Ti-Zr alloys suggest that Zr can be a promising element for suppressing inflammatory-induced corrosion in case of other Ti-based materials such as alloys from Ti-Mo group. For Ti-12Mo alloy, substitution of Ti atoms to Zr atoms should be firstly analyzed from mechanical perspective to preserve advantageous TRIP/TWIP effects for strain-hardening and ductility. In the TRIP/TWIP Ti alloys design, Zr exhibits a weak stabilizing effect on the beta phase, while significantly influencing the stress-induced martensitic transformation as its content increases in the Ti-12Mo alloy. The progressive addition of Zr enhances the mechanical stability of the beta phase, leading to a transition from TRIP to TWIP deformation mechanisms. Specifically, TRIP dominates in Ti-12Mo-3Zr, a combination of TRIP and TWIP is observed in Ti-12Mo-5Zr and Ti-12Mo-6Zr, and TWIP becomes dominant in Ti-12Mo-10Zr [35,36].

Considering all of the described aspects the aim of this work was to compare corrosion properties of Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr alloys in the inflammatory conditions that are relevant for the post-implantation period. Performed experiments were focused on finding responses to the following questions:

- (i) How does the partial substitution of the Ti by Zr atoms affect corrosion resistance of Ti-Mo alloy in the presence of inflammatory fluid?
- (ii) How is the corrosion process of Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr influenced by cathodic polarization?

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Tested materials

Ti-12Mo (wt %) and Ti-12Mo-5Zr (wt %) alloys were produced using

the arc-melting technique from pure alloying elements (titanium, molybdenum and zirconium). Both alloys were re-melted five times under high purity argon gas. Arc-melted ingots (around 25 g each) were then heat-treated at $950\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min under a high vacuum atmosphere (10^{-5} mbar) and quenched in room-temperature water. Then, the ingots were cold-rolled down to 0.6 mm thickness (reduction rate $> 90\%$). Cold-rolled samples were subsequently recrystallized at $950\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min and water-quenched, which resulted in the formation of homogeneous mono-phase microstructure composed from micrometric equiaxed grains of beta phase (Fig. 1a, b). These plates were used as a tested material for further corrosion measurements and for verification of their mechanical performance by conventional uniaxial tensile tests. The microstructure of non-deformed and deformed samples was analyzed by electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD) technique with a Hitachi SU-70 microscope. Mechanical tests were conducted with an INSTRON 5982 machine. Specimens for mechanical tests were 4 mm in width and 0.64 mm in thickness. In order to have a view of mechanical performance, the following parameters were designated from the results of tensile tests: (i) yield strength (YS), (ii) ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and (iii) uniform elongation. Values obtained for tested alloys were as follows: Ti-12Mo (i) YS = 625 MPa, (ii) UTS = 750 MPa, (iii) uniform elongation = 40%; Ti-12Mo-5Zr (i) YS = 650 MPa, (ii) UTS = 750 MPa, (iii) uniform elongation = 28%. Ti-12Mo-5Zr alloy demonstrates similar mechanical strength to Ti-12Mo with simultaneously satisfactory ductility. This is related to the ability of activation of additional deformation mechanisms to dislocation slip, precisely the TWIP/TRIP effect. For both alloys typical band like deformation products are detected in the deformed samples. The typical $\{3\ 3\ 2\} <1\ 1\ 3>$ twinning structures [37] are shown in Fig. 1c and d.

2.2. Electrochemical studies

Corrosion response of Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr alloy (in non-deformed state: Fig. 1a, b) was analyzed in PBS + 0.1 M H_2O_2 (pH = 7.4, temp. $37\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) under free corrosion conditions as well as under cathodic polarization. Concentration of H_2O_2 was selected based on previous experiments performed for orthopedic Ti-6Al-4V alloy [21,24,25]. Corrosion resistance under free corrosion conditions was

Fig. 1. EBSD maps with the microstructure of Ti-Mo and Ti-Mo-Zr alloys: a), b) before and c), d) after conventional uniaxial tensile tests. Note equiaxed grains of beta-phase observed before mechanical tests and formation of deformation twins within beta-grains for the loaded samples.

evaluated based on electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) performed at open circuit potential (OCP) with an amplitude ± 10 mV. The electrochemical potential was measured vs. Ag/AgCl/KCl (sat) electrode and all potential values presented in the further part of this study are by default provided in V vs. Ag/AgCl/KCl (sat). For a counter electrode, a platinum plate was selected. EIS tests were performed from 1000 Hz down to 0.01 Hz with a Metrohm Vionic potentiostat. Before EIS tests, the electrochemical potential value was controlled for 5100 s. Tests for both Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr were performed three times. Obtained data were then analyzed by fitting electrical circuit using NOVA software. This procedure allowed for determination of oxide layer resistance (R_{ox}), which correlates with the protective properties of oxide layer in PBS + 0.1 M H_2O_2 solution. Statistically significant differences in R_{ox} values obtained for Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr were determined with ANOVA analysis (one-way analysis of variance) with a Tukey's procedure ($\alpha = 0.05$) [38]. Kinetics of dissolution at OCP and under cathodic polarization were verified using atomic emission spectroelectrochemistry (AESEC). AESEC allows for the determination of the concentration of metal ions dissolved into the flowing fluid during the electrochemically controlled process using spectrometer (Horiba Ultima 2C) [39,40]. The atomic emission intensity is measured as a function of time during an electrochemical experiment. Using standard calibration methods, elemental concentration (C_M) vs. time profiles were obtained. Finally, the concentration was transformed to the elemental dissolution rate (ν_M) according to Equation (1), where A is the surface area exposed to the fluid (1 cm² in our case) and f is a flow rate (1.0 ml per minute in our case) [41,42]. The following detection limits for particular elements were obtained under the conditions of our experiments: (i) Ti: 0.002 ppm, (ii) Mo: 0.008 ppm, (iii) Zr: 0.008 ppm. To verify selective dissolution during the corrosion process, the dissolution rates of molybdenum (Mo) and zirconium (Zr) were normalized (ν'_M) against the base element, titanium (Ti) using Eq. (2), where X_{Ti} and X_M represent the weight percentages of titanium and alloying elements respectively [43]. It can be assumed that selective dissolution of particular alloying element takes place when $\nu'_M > \nu_{Ti}$ [44]. In contrast, the corrosion process can enrich alloying elements on the alloy surface. Dissolution rate was also converted to dissolution current (j_M) using Eq. (3), where F, M_M and Z_M represents Faraday's constant, molar mass of particular element and expected numbers of electrons exchanged per atom during the process respectively [45]. The sum of ν_M or j_M calculated for Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr alloys is marked as ν_Σ and j_Σ . During AESEC experiments electrochemical signal was applied and monitored with a potentiostat a Gamry Reference 600. Signal intensity related to dissolved ions was recorded along with the electrochemical response during the subsequent electrochemical procedure: (i) OCP monitoring for 1200 s, (ii) potentiostatic polarization at -1 V vs. Ag/AgCl/KCl (sat) for 1200 s, (iii) OCP monitoring for 2700 s.

$$\nu_M = f \frac{C_M}{A} \quad (1)$$

$$\nu'_M = \left(\frac{X_{Ti}}{X_M} \right) \nu_M \quad (2)$$

$$j_M = F \frac{\nu_M Z_M}{M_M} \quad (3)$$

2.3. Surface analysis

Surface analysis included the following steps: (i) analysis of oxide layer stoichiometry with X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) a Microlab Thermo Electron (ii) top-view analysis of surface morphology with a scanning electron microscope (SEM) a Helios 5 UX DualBeam, Thermo Fisher Scientific, and (iii) cross-section analysis of the oxide layer thickness with a transmission electron microscope (TEM) a Jeol F200. All microscopy investigations were conducted for non-immersed

samples and for samples subjected to selected variants of corrosion experiments. Specimens for TEM observations were prepared using a focus ion beam microscope-scanning electron microscope (FIB-SEM) a Helios 5 UX DualBeam (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Before FIB cutting process, specimen surfaces were protected by carbon layer. Details related to XPS and microscopy analysis are included elsewhere [33].

3. Results

3.1. Materials behavior under free corrosion conditions

Fig. 2 presents the OCP as a function of time during immersion in PBS + 0.1 M H_2O_2 for 5100 s before EIS measurements. It can be noticed that the potential values registered for Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr were very close to each other, with the biggest difference (around 40 mV) found after the first few minutes of immersion. For both alloys a slight but systematic increase of potential values was visible during the time of their exposure to the inflammatory fluid, which indicate the progressive formation of the oxide film on alloys surfaces [46,47]. As OCP variations show only the tendency to corrosion, EIS tests were performed in order to gain quantitative information about the protective properties of the oxide formed on Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr alloys during immersion in PBS + H_2O_2 . Fig. 3a. shows Bode plots, which illustrate the impedance response of Ti-Mo and Ti-Mo-Zr alloys after 5100 s of their exposure to the PBS + 0.1 M H_2O_2 at OCP. Properties of the oxide layers were evaluated based on the values of oxide layer resistance (R_{ox}), designated by fitting the Randles-CPE circuit to the experimental EIS data (Fig. 3b). Fitted data revealed that Ti-Mo-Zr demonstrates better protective properties of barrier oxide film compared to Ti-Mo. Average R_{ox} value designated for Ti-Mo-Zr was around two times greater compared to Ti-Mo alloy (Fig. 3b). Differences in the corrosion response were found to be significantly important at $\alpha = 0.05$ level. Electrochemical data correlates with surface morphology presented in SEM micrographs. Oxide film formed on Ti-Mo during immersion in the inflammatory fluid exhibits a typical H_2O_2 -induced nanopopography, whereas no significant corrosion changes were observed on Ti-Mo-Zr after short-term immersion in PBS + 0.1 M H_2O_2 (Fig. 4).

3.2. Corrosion behavior under cathodic polarization

Fig. 5 presents AESEC dissolution profiles (ν_M and ν'_M) registered for Ti and alloying elements at OCP and under potentiostatic polarization at -1 V. It can be clearly seen that applying cathodic potential resulted in

Fig. 2. OCP variation during immersion of Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr in PBS + 0.1 M H_2O_2 .

Fig. 3. Electrochemical response in PBS + 0.1 M H₂O₂ under free corrosion conditions: a) Bode plots which illustrate results of EIS tests, b) oxide layer resistances designated from EIS spectra, correspond to the corrosion resistance of tested materials. Note higher corrosion resistance for Ti-Mo-Zr alloy.

Fig. 4. SEM images captured for the surface of Ti-Mo and Ti-Mo-Zr alloys a),b) in the non-immersed state; c),d) after 5100 s of immersion in PBS + 0.1 M H₂O₂ at OCP. Note H₂O₂-induced formation of nanometric pits for Ti-Mo alloy and lack of corrosion changes for Ti-Mo-Zr alloy.

the rapid growth of elemental dissolution for both Ti-Mo and Ti-Mo-Zr alloys (Fig. 5c, d). After completing polarization and returning to the OCP, the ν_M gradually decreased towards the values observed just before applying the external potential (Fig. 5c, d). For Ti-Mo-Zr, ν_{Ti} reached its original level approx. 2700 s after finishing polarization. However for Ti-Mo ν_{Ti} did not return to this level throughout the entire duration of the experiment (Table 1). Considering normalized values (ν'_M) almost identical dissolution of Ti and Mo was registered in case of Ti-12Mo alloy, which indicates on their similar tendency to corrode under inflammatory and cathodic inflammatory conditions (Fig. 5e). Different findings were derived from ν'_M profiles recorded for Ti-12Mo-5Zr alloy (Fig. 5f). Although at OCP ν'_{Mo} and ν'_{Zr} were almost identical with ν_{Ti} ,

important discrepancies were found at $-1V$ (Fig. 5f). Preferential dissolution of Mo and suppressed dissolution of Zr, as compared to Ti, were observed during the whole time of cathodic polarization (Fig. 5f). Since the registered Mo dissolution values (ν_{Mo}) were similar for both Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr alloys (see Table 1), it can be inferred that the addition of Zr primarily inhibits the corrosion of Ti without significantly affecting the behavior of molybdenum. Furthermore, AESEC results clearly show that Zr is less prone to dissolve than titanium and molybdenum during cathodic polarization in a PBS solution containing H₂O₂. Values of total elemental dissolution rate ($\nu\Sigma$) calculated for Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr are presented in Fig. 6. Note that at OCP $\nu\Sigma$ was similar for both alloys (Fig. 6, Table 2). A significant difference in $\nu\Sigma$ was observed immediately after applying cathodic potential (Fig. 6). After approx. 100 s at $-1V$, $\nu\Sigma$ for Ti-12Mo was nearly 65 % higher compared to ternary alloy. However, the differences between the alloys decreased progressively with longer polarization times. At the end of polarization (see $t = 2350$ s, Fig. 6), the difference in $\nu\Sigma$ registered for tested alloys was reduced to 14 % (Table 2). This finding confirms that the beneficial effect of Zr is the most visible during the first 100 s of cathodic polarization. Note that total dissolution current ($j\Sigma$), calculated from AESEC polarization data, was more than 10 times lower compared to the electrochemical current (j_e) registered during polarization at $-1V$ (see Fig. 7, Table 2, 1200s-2400s of AESEC experiment). This confirms that despite accelerated elemental dissolution after applying cathodic potential, electrochemical process is dominated by reduction reactions (oxygen and hydrogen peroxide reduction).

SEM micrographs captured after AESEC experiments revealed uniform nanotopography for Ti-Mo and virtually a lack of corrosion-induced changes in the oxide layer formed on Ti-Mo-Zr alloy (Fig. 8). This observation confirmed that Zr suppresses corrosion-originated changes in the oxide morphology also when titanium alloy is subjected to the combined effect of H₂O₂ and cathodic polarization. Note that nanometric pits demonstrated greater dimensions when Ti-Mo alloy was subjected to cathodic polarization than when it was immersed for the same time in PBS + H₂O₂ fluid at OCP (Fig. 4c, Fig. 8c). This confirms that for Ti-12Mo H₂O₂-induced rebuilt of oxide of Ti-Mo is accelerated for alloy previously subjected to cathodic polarization.

Different corrosion response observed for Ti-Mo and Ti-Mo-Zr alloy is the resultant of different chemical composition of the oxide film formed on their surfaces. For both alloys peaks from all metallic elements and their oxides were identified on HR-XPS spectra (Fig. 9, Fig. 10) recorded before and after AESEC experiments conducted according to procedure presented in Fig. 5. Slight decrease in the content

Fig. 5. AESEC results registered for Ti-Mo and Ti-Mo-Zr in PBS + 0.1M H₂O₂ during the following experiment: (i) OCP monitoring, (ii) potentiostatic polarization at -1V vs. Ag/AgCl/KCl (sat) (iii) OCP monitoring. a),b) electrochemical potential; c), d) elemental dissolution rate (v_M); e),f) normalized elemental dissolution rate (v'_M); against the bulk element (Ti). For normalized dissolution, multiplicative factors for alloying elements were as follows: (i) Ti-Mo: Mo = 7.33, (ii) Ti-Mo-Zr: Mo = 6.92, Zr = 16.6. Note congruent dissolution of Ti and Mo for Ti-Mo and suppressed dissolution of Ti and Zr for Ti-Mo-Zr alloy.

Table 1

Elemental dissolution rate (v_M) [$\text{ng}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$] designated for Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr based on AESEC data registered at OCP and during particular steps of cathodic polarization.

		OCP (t = 1150 s)	-1V (dissolution peak)	-1V (t = 2350 s)	OCP (t = 5050 s)
Ti-12Mo	Ti	0.53	12.11	6.67	0.70
	Mo	0.049	1.68	0.81	0.12
Ti-12Mo-5Zr	Ti	0.27	6.54	5.33	0.27
	Mo	0.048	1.23	0.97	0.053
	Zr	0.002	0.29	0.25	0.004

of Ti₂O₃ and TiO oxides was observed after corrosion tests, which indicates progressive oxidation of both alloys during immersion in PBS + H₂O₂ solution despite conducting cathodic polarization (Fig. 11). For Ti-Mo-Zr alloy, an increase of ZrO₂ content can be noticed after AESEC procedure (Fig. 11). Concentration of Zr in the oxide layer of polarized Ti-Mo-Zr sample (almost 10 at. %) was significantly greater compared to alloy stoichiometry (approx. 2.86 at. % which corresponds to 5 wt. %). This can be related to the suppressed dissolution of Zr observed during

cathodic polarization (see Fig. 5) and its preferential oxidation during further immersion in PBS + H₂O₂ at OCP.

3.3. Effect of cathodic polarization on the oxide layer evolution

As corrosion analysis indicates that the Ti-Mo-Zr alloy shows more potential from the application point of view, further investigation was focused on understanding the evolution of the oxide layer during longer

Fig. 6. Total elemental dissolution rate registered for Ti-Mo and Ti-Mo-Zr in PBS + 0.1M H₂O₂ during following experiment: (i) OCP monitoring, (ii) potentiostatic polarization at -1V (iii) OCP monitoring. Note the immediate growth of dissolution rate at the beginning of polarization and higher total elemental dissolution for Ti-Mo alloy during polarization step.

immersion times (5 days) in PBS + H₂O₂ (Fig. 12). Top-view SEM images revealed developed nano-sponge like morphology for both samples exposed to PBS + H₂O₂ at free corrosion conditions (Fig. 12b) and for the sample subjected to short cathodic polarization (20 min) and then remained in the solution at OCP (Fig. 12c). A HAADF STEM image in cross section revealed the presence of a porous oxide film of approximately 60 nm thickness, formed on the immersed materials (Fig. 12e, f). A high resolution TEM image of the native oxide film formed on the non-immersed Ti-12Mo-5Zr alloy indicated a thickness of 8–10 nm (Fig. 12g). The boundary between the native oxide layer and the metallic alloy is rather sharp and continuous, contrary to the developed and wavy character of the border found for immersed samples (Fig. 12g, h, i). The amorphous nature of the oxide was further confirmed by the presence of a characteristic halo in the fast Fourier transform (FFT) patterns obtained from the oxide film (Fig. 12h, i). The defective and porous structure of the oxide layer was observed in the HAADF STEM micrographs of the corroded samples, and was also evident in the cross-sectional EDS maps (Fig. 13), showing the distribution of oxygen. Note the variation in the oxygen content observed across the oxide film (Fig. 13). Near the bulk substrate (within approximately 12–15 nm from the surface), the oxide layer appeared significantly less porous, as indicated by a stronger oxygen signal. EDS maps confirmed that the oxide film formed in the solution contained Ti as well as both alloying elements (Mo and Zr). Enrichment in Zr in the outermost region of the oxide layer could be detected, which was particularly evident in the alloy subjected to cathodic polarization (Fig. 13). It is important to note that changes in contrast in EDS maps reflect the surface distribution of the detected counts for specific chemical elements. As a result, these maps provide only qualitative information about the chemical

composition. Therefore, differences in contrast and intensity between elements should not be directly compared.

4. Discussion

This study focuses on exploring how the addition of Zr to the Ti-12Mo alloy affects its corrosion behavior in the physiological fluid. Selected methodology simulated harsh conditions that can be created during inflammatory reactions of the immunological system [13,48–50]. Literature studies on commercially used titanium materials have shown that reactive inflammatory species, such as hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), can induce the evolution of titanium oxide film, which includes an increase in the density of oxygen vacancies within the film [25]. The extent of inflammatory corrosion is related not only to the chemistry of the peri-implant environment but also to the electrochemical conditions, which can be influenced by daily activities [21,23,24,42]. *In vitro* studies have demonstrated that Ti-6Al-4V, commonly used in orthopedic implants, can undergo cathodic polarization during fretting [26], which further accelerates corrosion in the presence of inflammatory products [23]. Here, we examined this aspect by investigating the inflammatory-induced degradation of Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr under both free corrosion conditions (at OCP) and under cathodic bias.

As with other studies related to titanium biomaterials [49,51–53], we monitored alloys degradation under free corrosion conditions using the EIS method. Higher R_{ox} value calculated for Ti-12Mo-5Zr alloy indicates its better corrosion resistance in PBS + H₂O₂ (Fig. 3). Contrary to Ti-12Mo, no morphological changes induced by corrosion were visible in the post-immersion SEM images, which also confirms advantageous corrosion performance of ternary alloy (Fig. 4). Considering the same type of microstructure with similar grains dimensions (Fig. 1) as well as the same weight percentage (X_M) of Mo in Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr

Fig. 7. Total elemental dissolution current (j_Z) [$\mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$] and electrochemical current [j_e] [$\mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$] registered for Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr during 1200 s of cathodic polarization at -1V in PBS + 0.1M H₂O₂.

Table 2

Total elemental dissolution rate (ν_Z) [$\text{ng}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$], total dissolution current (j_Z) [$\mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$] and electrochemical current (j_e) [$\mu\text{A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$] calculated for Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr based on AESEC data registered at OCP and during particular steps of cathodic polarization.

	OCP (t = 1150 s)	-1V (dissolution peak)			-1V (t = 2350 s)			OCP (t = 5050 s)
	ν_Z	ν_Z	j_Z	j_e	ν_Z	j_Z	j_e	ν_Z
Ti-12Mo	0.58	13.48	100.36	1674	7.48	57.12	1757	0.82
Ti-12Mo-5Zr	0.32	8.18	59.66	1862	6.56	48.19	1775	0.32

Fig. 8. SEM images captured for the surface of Ti-Mo and Ti-Mo-Zr alloys a),b) in the non-immersed state; c),d) after following experiment: (i) OCP monitoring, (ii) potentiostatic polarization at $-1V$ (iii) OCP monitoring. Note the formation of sponge-like nanotopography for Ti-Mo exposed to PBS + 0.1 M H_2O_2 and the lack of corrosion changes for Ti-Mo-Zr alloy.

alloys, it can be clearly stated that difference in corrosion properties is related to the partial substitution of Ti by Zr atoms and thereby formation of ZrO_2 on Ti-12Mo-5Zr surface. Electrochemical response recorded by EIS reflects the combined currents associated with both the dissolution of metal and the growth of the oxide layer. This makes it difficult to determine the mechanism of Zr/ ZrO_2 contribution to corrosion process based solely on EIS data. Supplementing EIS with AESEC studies shed a light on the origin of better properties observed for Ti-12Mo-5Zr under free corrosion conditions (Fig. 5). As virtually no differences were observed in the $\nu\Sigma$ of alloys at OCP, it can be concluded that higher R_{ox} value found for Ti-12Mo-5Zr is related rather to the suppressed oxide film growth. Overall results indicate that for a short exposure time in PBS + H_2O_2 at free corrosion conditions, Zr or ZrO_2 block or suppress formation of nanoporous oxide film that was found for corroded Ti-12Mo alloy.

When cathodic potential was applied, a rapid decrease in corrosion resistance was observed for both tested alloys (Fig. 5, Fig. 6). To date, deleterious effect of cathodic polarization on the corrosion resistance of titanium-based biomaterials was confirmed based on EIS studies [23,24]. EIS data registered in PBS + H_2O_2 have shown that sustained cathodic bias at $-1V$ can decrease oxide layer resistance for Ti-6Al-4V by three orders of magnitude [24]. Our data clearly show that cathodic-induced deterioration in corrosion resistance of Ti-6Al-4V is associated to the enhanced ν_M (Fig. 5, Fig. 6). As it is visible in AESEC spectra, substantial increase in ν_M took place immediately after applying cathodic potential (Fig. 5, Fig. 6). This behavior may be related to

increased level of oxide film defectiveness, making it more prone to interact with H_2O_2 [25]. For binary alloy, the $\nu\Sigma$ within the first 100 s of polarization was substantially higher compared to the ternary one. Additionally, AESEC studies revealed a changing nature of the dissolution process during sustained cathodic polarization. For both alloys, the ν_M began to decrease during polarization after immediate growth observed within the first seconds (Fig. 5, Fig. 6). This can be related to the lowering of H_2O_2 content near alloys surfaces owing to its progressive reduction at cathodic potentials [42]. The decrease in the $\nu\Sigma$ was evidently greater for Ti-Mo alloy, making the difference between alloys less important when the polarization was longer (Fig. 6). Considering the fact that Zr and/or ZrO_2 suppress oxide growth at free corrosion conditions, it can be assumed that it can also block increasing of defectiveness or other changes in the oxide film induced by cathodic potential. This can explain significantly lower dissolution observed for Ti-12Mo-5Zr during the initial stage of polarization and the more constant dissolution rate during sustained cathodic polarization of the Ti-12Mo-5Zr alloy. The less altered oxide film could be less sensitive to the variation of the H_2O_2 concentration near the surface.

During cathodic polarization, the elemental ν_M was almost perfectly congruent for Ti-12Mo alloy, while for Ti-12Mo-5Zr the dissolution of Mo was preferential to Ti (Fig. 5). As dissolution of Mo was similar for both alloys, we can assume that Zr suppresses mostly dissolution of Ti. Additionally, the ν_M during the cathodic process was the lowest for Zr. This can be attributed to the fact that neither Zr nor ZrO_2 are reported to form highly hydrated complexes with H_2O_2 , unlike Ti [34] and Mo [54].

Fig. 9. Elemental XPS spectra recorded for Ti-Mo alloy in non-immersed state (top line) and after following experiment (bottom line): (i) OCP monitoring, (ii) potentiostatic polarization at -1V vs. $\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}/\text{KCl}$ (sat) (iii) OCP monitoring. Mo-O^* corresponds to Mo_4O_{11} or $\text{Mo}(\text{OH})^*/\text{Mo}$.

Reduced dissolution of Zr during cathodic potential, along with its privileged oxidation during subsequent immersion at OCP, can explain the excessive amount of ZrO_2 detected by XPS after AESEC experiments (Fig. 11). We hypothesize that by suppressing dissolution at cathodic potentials as well as suppressing oxidation at OCP, ZrO_2 stabilizes the oxide layer formed on Ti-12Mo-5Zr, which is predominantly composed of titanium oxides. This stabilization is evidenced by the lack of significant morphological changes observed for Ti-12Mo-5Zr after short-term immersion at OCP (Fig. 4b, d) and after AESEC tests, which included cathodic polarization (Fig. 8b, d).

To verify if the presence of Zr suppresses the formation of nanometric pits or blocks this process in the long-term, microscopy observations were repeated after 5 days of immersion in $\text{PBS} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$. Top-view SEM observations revealed that, contrary to the non-immersed material, the Ti-12Mo-5Zr surface exposed to inflammatory solution demonstrated a nanoporous morphology regardless electrochemical conditions (Fig. 12). For corroded samples an oxygen gradient was visible across the oxide film, with noticeably stronger oxygen signal next to surface of bulk alloy (Fig. 13). It is well known that spontaneously formed titanium oxide films demonstrate a reverse oxygen gradient, with increasing oxygen content from the alloy surface toward the outermost part of the film [55]. Thereby, the stronger oxygen signal close to the bulk alloy surface indicates that the native oxide film did not dissolve during

interaction with H_2O_2 but rather become more defective. The oxygen-enriched region of the oxide film was difficult to distinguish owing to its fuzzy appearance, however its thickness was estimated to be around 12–15 nm for both corroded samples (Fig. 13). No difference found for polarized and non-polarized alloy suggest that sustained cathodic polarization at -1V in $\text{PBS} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ ($\text{pH} = 7.4$) did not result in the dissolution of the oxide film. Instead, it facilitated ion transport across the oxide. Five days of Ti-12Mo-5Zr immersion at free corrosion conditions resulted in the built-up of the oxide film with high porosity, which achieved around 60 nm for both polarized and non-polarized states (Fig. 12, Fig. 13). Additionally, the outermost part of the oxide film formed in the solution was enriched with Zr (Fig. 13), which is in agreement with the increase of the ZrO_2 content detected after AESEC experiments based on XPS measurements (Fig. 11).

The overall results indicate that prolonged exposure to the $\text{PBS} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ at free corrosion conditions induce the growth of a porous oxide film enriched with ZrO_2 . The thicknesses were similar for both the previously polarized and the non-polarized Ti-12Mo-5Zr. This result suggests that a short cathodic polarization does not affect the characteristics of the oxide film, which is built-up during further immersion in $\text{PBS} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ at OCP. However, the AESEC data clearly shows that applying a cathodic potential immediately enhances the dissolution of Ti-12Mo-5Zr in $\text{PBS} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ (Fig. 5, Fig. 6). This situation can happen

Fig. 10. Elemental XPS spectra recorded for Ti-Mo-Zr alloy in non-immersed state (top line) and after following experiment (bottom line): (i) OCP monitoring, (ii) potentiostatic polarization at $-1V$ vs. $Ag/AgCl/KCl$ (sat) (iii) OCP monitoring. Mo-O* corresponds to Mo_4O_{11} or $Mo(OH)^x/Mo$.

Fig. 11. Composition of the oxide layer formed on non-immersed Ti-Mo and Ti-Mo-Zr and on materials subjected to following experiment (polarized): (i) OCP monitoring, (ii) potentiostatic polarization at $-1V$ vs. $Ag/AgCl/KCl$ (sat) (iii) OCP monitoring. Note greater content of ZrO_2 for polarized Ti-Mo-Zr.

repeatedly *in vivo* near regions exposed to fretting areas, where the inflammatory reaction of the immunological system is promoted by the released corrosion products [56]. Thereby, our study highlights that the potential degradation-related consequences of the fretting process should be considered and predicted not only for the mechanically abraded area but also for the adjacent regions.

5. Conclusions

This study was focused on evaluating and comparing the corrosion resistance of Ti-12Mo and Ti-12Mo-5Zr in the conditions that simulates inflammation as can be found in peri-implant region. Alloys were tested in one of the harshest conditions that can happen *in vivo*, including the presence of inflammatory species such as H_2O_2 and cathodic

Fig. 12. Oxide layer evolution during 5 days of Ti-Mo-Zr exposure in PBS + 0.1 M H₂O₂ at OCP. Experiment was performed for non-polarized sample (middle column) as well as for sample that was previously polarized (right column). a),b),c) top-view SEM images illustrate surface morphology; d),e), f) cross-section HAADF STEM images illustrate structure and thickness of the oxide layers; g),h),i) high resolution TEM images with fast Fourier transforms (FFT) for corroded samples. Note amorphous character of the oxide film.

Fig. 13. EDS maps with Ti, O, Mo and Zr distribution across the Ti-Mo-Zr surface. Note the growth of the porous oxide during 5 days of immersion in PBS + 0.1 M H₂O₂ and corrosion changes within the part of oxide film that is adjacent to the alloy substrate (for both non-polarized sample and for sample previously polarized at -1V for 20 minutes).

polarization which is relevant for implants exposed to fretting. The following findings were derived from the experiments:

- Electrochemical studies at OCP revealed that Ti-12Mo-5Zr alloy demonstrated better corrosion performance in PBS + H₂O₂ compared to Ti-12Mo, which was reflected by greater oxide layer resistance. A similar level of dissolution rate ($\nu\Sigma$), registered at OCP for both alloys, indicates that the difference in oxide film resistance is related to the suppression of oxide growth for Ti-12Mo-5Zr. The presence of Zr and thereby ZrO₂ in the oxide film formed on Ti-12Mo-5Zr is responsible for this characteristic.
- Cathodic polarization resulted in a rapid increase in the elemental dissolution rate (ν_M), which was less substantial for Ti-12Mo-5Zr alloy. This can be related to the presence of ZrO₂ in the oxide formed on Ti-12Mo-5Zr. Zirconium oxide is expected to suppress oxide film growth at OCP as well as should suppress cathodic-induced increase of defectiveness within the film.
- For the Ti-12Mo alloy almost perfectly congruent dissolution of Ti and Mo was registered during cathodic polarization. For Ti-12Mo-5Zr dissolution of Ti was suppressed compared to Mo. It was found that Zr and/or ZrO₂ block the dissolution of Ti without any significant influence on the Mo behavior.
- Prolonged exposure (5 days) of Ti-12Mo-5Zr at OCP in PBS + H₂O₂ resulted in the growth of the nanometric (about 60 nm) porous oxide film. Thickness of this oxide was not affected by previously performed short cathodic polarization.
- In summary, this study provides evidence about the beneficial role of Zr in suppressing inflammatory-induced corrosion of Ti-Mo beta phase alloy. The mechanism of corrosion enhancement depends on electrochemical conditions. At OCP Zr suppress oxide layer growth, while under cathodic polarization conditions Zr suppress Ti dissolution.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Agata Sotniczuk: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Witold Chromiński:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Damian Kalita:** Methodology, Investigation. **Halina Garbacz:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Chenyang Xie:** Methodology, Investigation. **Junhui Tang:** Methodology, Investigation. **Baojie Dou:** Methodology, Investigation. **Marcin Pisarek:** Methodology, Investigation. **Aleksandra Baron-Wiechec:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Data curation. **Łukasz Kurpaska:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Fan Sun:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Investigation. **Kevin Ogle:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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